

Effect of Sucrose Immersion on Retinal Tissue Damage of Adult Zebrafish

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Abstract

Sucrose is a disaccharide macronutrient consisting of glucose and fructose. Sucrose can directly enter the bloodstream and increase blood glucose levels and increase the risk of type 2 diabetes which is characterized by hyperglycemia. Chronic conditions of hyperglycemia contribute to complications of diabetic retinopathy (DR). ganglion cell death results in the thinning of the Inner Plexiform Layer (IPL) which appears in the early stages of diabetic retinopathy. The research aims to prove the effect of sucrose induction at a dose of 1%, 2% and 4% on retinal damage in adult *Danio rerio*.

The research was conducted in a laboratory with post test control group design. Subjects using adult male *Danio rerio* aged 4-5 months, consisting of a control group (P0), sucrose treatment groups of 1% (P1), 2% (P2) and 4% (P4). Each group consisted of 30 heads induced for 28 days. The euthanasia process is through soaking with ice water for 10 minutes. The collection of the eyeball is followed by making histological preparations of retinal tissue with HE staining. Ganglionic cell apoptosis was calculated manually by field of view, while IPL thickness was measured using ImageJ software. Data analysis using One way ANOVA with $p < 0.05$.

Sucrose induction in the P1, P2, P3 groups for 28 days led to an increase in ganglion cell apoptosis of 91.00 ± 6.66 ; 94.00 ± 2.28 ; 129.17 ± 10.79 compared to P0 15.00 ± 5.65 with $p < 0.05$, and a decrease in IPL thickness of 96.17 ± 8.65 ; 90.17 ± 12.54 ; $(72.17 \pm 7.11 \mu\text{m})$ compared to P0 $131.33 \pm 16.15 \mu\text{m}$ with $p < 0.05$. The doses of P1 and P2 did not differ significantly but differed significantly from P3 in the number of cells undergoing apoptosis and IPL thickness. The higher the dose, the greater the effect. Conclusion. Sucrose immersion can increase retinal damage in zebrafish induced by 4% sucrose immersion.

Keywords: Zebrafish, sucrose, retina

Introduction

Sucrose (sugar) is a disaccharide formed by glucose and fructose and is an important macronutrient for maintaining normal physiological activities and functions (Ranjan *et al.*, 2018). In sucrose metabolism, glucose will be used first after transporting into the intracellular using a Na^+ transporter/glucose co-transporter facilitated diffusion (GLUT), while the fructose will be stored in adipose tissue. A diet high in sucrose, especially foods that contain excessive amounts of glucose and fructose, in the long term can cause obesity and diabetes mellitus (DM) (Laville *et al.*, 2009).

DM is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by increased blood glucose levels. A person is said to be hyperglycemic if a fasting blood glucose level of $>126 \text{ mg/dL}$ or the baseline blood glucose level of $>200 \text{ mg/dL}$ (Perkeni, 2021). The most common type of diabetes, namely type 2 DM, occurs due to insulin resistance in the tissue or insulin production cannot meet needs (Farid *et al.*, 2014).

The global prevalence of DM in adults aged 20-79 years was 6.4% or 285 million in 2010, and will increase to 7.7% or 439 million in 2030 (Perkeni *et al.*, 2021). Indonesia ranks 5th in the world as the country with the highest number of type 2 DM sufferers. WHO estimates that the number of type 2 DM patients in Indonesia will increase from 8.4 million in 2000 to around 21.3 million in 2030 (WHO, 2016), and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimates that in 2019-2030 there will be an increase of 10.7 million to 13.7 million (IDF, 2019), with the prevalence of DR sufferers among DM patients worldwide estimated at 34.6% (93 million people) (Mitchell *et al.*, 2008).

Hyperglycemia is a risk factor that contributes to the development of diabetic retinopathy (Yang *et al.*, 2024). Chronic hyperglycemia increases the production of excitotoxic metabolites (glutamate, branch chain amino acid, and homocysteine) which have the potential to cause damage to neurons. The increase in excitotoxic metabolites activates several metabolic pathways such as protein kinase C, AGEs (Advance Glycation End Products), and the hexaminase pathway which results in increased oxidative stress and decreased levels of neurotrophic factors resulting in apoptosis in retinal ganglion cells (Ola *et al.*, 2013). The decrease in the number of nerve cells due to apoptosis contributes to changes in the morphology and thickness of the retina and is associated with retinopathy. Retinal ischemia causes increased expression of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), resulting in the formation of new blood vessels accompanied by transient fibroglial structures, promoting the proliferation of new fibrovascular tissue from the retinal surface into the vitreal cavity (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007). Damage to the blood vessel barrier in the retina which causes leakage and accumulation of fluid in the intraretinal layer can also cause decreased macular function (Septadina, 2015). The macula or macula lutea is the posterior proportion of the retina composed of two or more layers of ganglionic cells with a diameter of 5-6 mm and is located between the arcus of temporal vascularization, in which the middle part (fovea centralis) is rich in xanthophyll pigment and photoreceptor cells, especially cone cells (Midena, 1997). Decreased retinal function is linear with decreased macular function (Septadina, 2015). If chronic hyperglycemia is not treated, vision loss usually occurs within two years after the onset of proliferative retinopathy (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007 and Septadina, 2015).

Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) have high genetic, anatomical and physiological similarities to humans. This is shown by a comparison of the zebrafish and human genomes, reaching 70% of the same genes. 84% of human genes known to be associated with human diseases are also found in zebrafish (Shehwana *et al.*, 2019). Experiments that were previously limited to whole retina studies due to challenges in rod-dominated models in rodents, make zebrafish a good model for retina studies because the zebrafish retina is rich in cone cells that allow for experiments. Zebrafish provide a more suitable model for studying ocular pathology (Jaroszynska *et al.*, 2021).

Previous research conducted by Gleeson *et al.* (2007) regarding zebrafish as a model of diabetic retinopathy showed that there was a significant decrease in the thickness of the IPL inner plexiform layer (IPL) by around 60% after application of 1% glucose to water for 28 days, and the research conducted by Singh *et al.* (2019) on zebrafish as a model of diabetic retinopathy using zebrafish embryos exposed to 4% and 5% glucose alternately for 5 days showed general changes in eye morphology, and a significant reduction in IPL thickness (29, 4%) at five dpf and a significant increase in INL thickness (42.3% to 4%) (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007 and Singh *et al.*, 2019). Research conducted by Sharma related to the regeneration of zebrafish retinal tissue where sucrose can increase ROS which causes apoptosis in retinal ganglion cells (Sharma *et al.*, 2019).

Based on the facts mentioned above, research was conducted to prove the effect of sucrose induction for 28 days on the number of ganglion cell apoptosis and IPL thickness of the zebrafish retina *in vivo*.

Research Methods

Research Design, Place and Time

The research was carried out in a laboratory, with a post test control group design to determine changes in the histology of the zebrafish retina. The stages of rearing, acclimatization, dissection of test fish, and retinal removal were carried out at the Fish Cultivation Laboratory, Fish Reproduction Division, Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Sciences (FPIK), Brawijaya University, Malang. Making retinal histology preparations, observing and scoring apoptosis and retinal IPL thickness were carried out at the Anatomical Pathology Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine (FK), Brawijaya University, Malang. The research was carried out in August-December 2023.

Treatment of Experimental Animals

This research used adult male zebrafish (*D. rerio*), the average weight of the six fish samples was 5-9 grams, and average age was 4-5 months. In healthy condition and without defects. The research group consisted of a control group (P0), a sucrose treatment group at a dose of 1% (P1), a dose of 2% (P2) and a dose of 4% (P3) in 2 liters of water (Dorsemans *et al.*, 2017). Each group consisted of 30 zebrafish. The induction water is changed every 2 days to avoid the growth of bacteria or other microorganisms (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007).

The zebrafish acclimatization process was adapted to constant laboratory conditions (14 hours of light, 10 hours of light and dark cycles, food, water, 28°C) for 1 week, with a frequency of feeding pellets 3 times every day, namely morning, afternoon and evening. After acclimatization, sucrose

induction was administered for 28 days to zebrafish experimental animals. At the end of treatment on day 29 before surgery, the zebrafish were fasted for more than 12 hours, then the zebrafish were euthanized using cold water for 10 minutes. After the zebrafish is unconscious, the fish is sacrificed for surgery and the eye organs are removed. The entire eye is removed from the fish's body by dividing the brain stem with a rostral-caudal incision through the brain. Zebrafish retinal tissue was blocked in paraffin for histology preparation with HE staining

Making Retinal Histology Preparations with Hematoxylin Eosin (HE) Staining

Eyes were incubated in 10% formalin phosphate buffer solution at temperature for one week. The eyes (trimming) are sliced to a thickness of $\pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ so they can be inserted into a cassette for processing in a tissue processor. Next, the dehydration process was carried out with 70%, 80% and 96% alcohol for 2 hours each. Tissue slides were placed in liquid paraffin at a temperature of 56°C for 2 hours twice. Staining was carried out by preparing on a glass object soaked in xylol I, II and III for 5 minutes each. Then the preparation was soaked in 96%, 80% and 70% alcohol for 5 minutes each, then washed with distilled water, then soaked in Hematoxylin Eosin for 7 minutes. The preparations were dried and mounted using entelan (glue) (Isaac *et al.*, 2023).

Calculation of the Apoptosis Number of Zebra Fish Retinal Ganglion Cells (*D. rerio*)

Retinal preparations that had undergone HE staining were then calculated for retinal ganglion cell apoptosis using a trinocular microscope with 400x magnification in 10 fields of view for each preparation. Calculation of the number of retinal ganglion cell apoptosis was carried out manually with the help of the ImageJ application and observed by 3 observers using the blind method. Ganglion cell apoptosis is characterized by pyknotic/shrinking nuclei and apoptotic cells appearing as round/oval masses with dark eosinophilic cytoplasm and dense chromatin nuclear fragments (Lim *et al.*, 2020). Calculation of retinal ganglion cell apoptosis is as follows.

$$(\%) = \frac{a}{b} \times 100\%$$

Formula 1. Calculation proportion of apoptosis

Note: a = Number of ganglion cell apoptosis in 1 field of view. b = Total number of ganglion cells in 1 field of view.

Changes in the Thickness of the Inner Plexiform Layer (IPL) of the Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) Retina

Retinal preparations that had undergone HE staining were observed under a trinocular microscope with 400x magnification, the preparations were photographed and transferred to ImageJ for measurement of the thickness of the inner plexiform layer (IPL), calculated from 10 fields of view by 3 different people. Data calculated by 3 observers were averaged to get the total results.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data are expressed in the form of mean \pm SD. Next, the data were statistically analyzed using one-way ANOVA to determine differences between groups with a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Further tests to determine the comparison of each treatment group used a post hoc test with a significance of $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis using SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solution) version 25.

Results And Data Analysis

Effect of Sucrose Induction on Apoptosis of Retinal Ganglion Cells in Zebrafish (*D. rerio*)

The results of calculating ganglion cell apoptosis can be seen in Table 1 and Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. Histopathological picture of zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retinal ganglion cell apoptosis (HE, 400x).

Left panel (P0) Normal control, (P1) 1% sucrose induction, (P2) 2% sucrose induction, (P3) 4% sucrose induction. (Black arrow) normal ganglion cells, (red arrow) pyknotic cells characterized by cell fragmentation in the form of a blackish purple color in the cell nucleus, (green arrow) apoptotic body. Right panel zoom in.

Figure 2. Histogram of average percentage of zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retinal ganglion cells apoptosis

Information:

G0: zebrafish in 2 L of aquarium water

G1: zebrafish with 1% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

G2: zebrafish with 2% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

G3: zebrafish with 4% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

n: number of samples

Table 1. Number of Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) Retinal Ganglion Cell Apoptosis induced by sucrose for 28 days

Group	n (sample)	Mean \pm SD Retinal Ganglion Cell Apoptotic (%)
Group G0	6	15,00 \pm 5,65
Group G1	6	46,00 \pm 6,66
Group G2	6	47,00 \pm 2,28
Group G3	6	65,17 \pm 10,79

Sucrose induction caused an increase in the number of ganglion cell apoptosis compared to the normal group, $p < 0.05$. The increase in the number of zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retinal ganglion cell apoptosis was 46%, 47%, 65% respectively in groups P1, P2, P3 compared to controls. Between treatment groups, it was found that P1 was not different from P2 but was significantly different from P3. The higher the dose, the greater the percentage of ganglion cells that experience apoptosis.

Effect of sucrose induction on the thickness of the retinal IPL layer of zebrafish (*D. rerio*).

The results of measuring the thickness of the zebrafish IPL layer induced by sucrose can be seen in Table 2 and, Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3. Histological image of the retinal layers of zebrafish (*D. rerio*) (HE, 400x).

There are 4 main layers in retinal tissue, including; (GL) ganglion layer, (IPL) inner plexiform layer, (INL) inner neural layer, (OPL) outer plexiform layer, (ONL) outer neural layer.

Figure 4. Histogram of the thickness of the IPL layer of the zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retina.

Information:

G0: zebrafish in 2 L of aquarium water

G1: zebrafish with 1% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

G2: zebrafish with 2% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

G3: zebrafish with 4% sucrose induction in 2L aquarium water

n : number of samples

Table 2. Results of Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) Retina IPL thickness analysis

Group	n (sample)	IPL Thickness (Mean ± SD)
Group G0	6	131,33 ± 16,15
Group G1	6	96,17 ± 8,65
Group G2	6	90,17 ± 12,54
Group G3	6	72,17 ± 7, 11

Discussion

Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) Retinal Ganglion Cell Apoptosis

Sucrose induction increases the percentage of zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retinal ganglion cell apoptosis compared to controls. This is thought to be due to an increase in blood glucose levels that occurred in the treatment group compared to the normal group (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007).

The research results showed that 4% sucrose induction for 28 days caused high levels of apoptosis. Hyperglycemia is the main factor in inducing diabetic retinopathy. Sucrose induction can cause hyperglycemia. The results of research conducted by Salsabila, 2024 ongoing, found that induction of sucrose doses of 1%, 2%, 4% in 2L of aquarium water for 28 days caused an increase in fasting blood glucose levels compared to normal. P1 blood glucose levels 131.67 ± 3.78 mg/dl are not significantly different compared to P2 137.83 ± 4.71 mg/dl and P0 84.17 ± 5.71 mg/dl, but are significantly different compared to P3 188.67 ± 15.97 mg/dl.

The sucrose solution will enter the blood through the digestive tract and gills, the sucrose will be converted into glucose and fructose. Glucose will be used first by the body. Chronically increasing blood glucose levels will cause insulin resistance, so that the glucose circulating in the blood cannot be used by cells, this results in hyperglycemia (Laville *et al.*, 2009). Chronic hyperglycemia increases ROS levels accompanied by a decrease in antioxidants in DM conditions, this causes damage to cell membrane lipids, damage to the cytoplasm, resulting in DNA chain damage which induces apoptosis. Exposure to chronic hyperglycemia also causes high levels of AGEs. Binding of AGEs and their receptor, RAGE, induces oxidative stress (Kowluru *et al.*, 2015). DM conditions activate the renin-angiotensin system found locally in the retina. The binding between angiotensin II and the AT1R receptor also induces oxidative stress in retinal neuron cells. Increased glutamate concentrations in DM cause excitatory disturbances in neurons resulting in excitotoxicity which induces cell apoptosis (Zong *et al.*, 2011).

The cell apoptosis that occurs causes glial cell reactivity. Glial cell reactivity induces pro-apoptotic factors. The relationship between apoptosis and glial cell reactivity runs both ways. Various studies show that in retinal neuron cells in DM sufferers there is a decrease in neuroprotective factors and high levels of various pro-apoptotic factors, so that high levels of apoptosis can be found in retinal ganglion cell tissue (Zong *et al.*, 2011).

Experimental and clinical studies suggest that neurodegenerative changes, including ganglion cell loss and glial reactivity are also early events in the pathogenesis of DR (Lim *et al.*, 2020). DR is associated with loss of retinal ganglion cells and death of ganglion cells which causes impaired visual function (Kim *et al.*, 2015). Zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retinal neurodegeneration is thought to occur before signs of changes in the microvascular system. Neurodegeneration occurs in two phases: direct damage to Retinal Ganglion Cells (RGCs) and secondary damage to RGCs due to non-neuronal cell responses. This secondary damage is considered to be the main cause of RGC loss, which occurs in diabetic retinopathy (Kern *et al.*, 2008).

The 4% sucrose dose induced more ganglion cell apoptosis than the 1% and 2% doses ($p < 0.05$). The results of this study are in line with previous research using mice (Park *et al.*, 2003). This is thought to be due to the influence of increasing blood glucose levels along with increasing sucrose doses given to each group resulting in increased ganglion cell apoptosis (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007 and Singh *et al.*, 2019).

Decreased Thickness of the Retinal IPL Layer of Zebrafish (*D. rerio*)

Sucrose induction doses of 1%, 2% and 4% caused a decrease in retinal thickness compared to controls. Loss of ganglion cells due to apoptosis accompanied by ganglion cell dysfunction causes a decrease in the thickness of the IPL layer of the zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retina (Gleeson *et al.*, 2007 and Nesper *et al.*, 2017). The Inner Plexiform Layer (IPL) of the retina consists of ganglion cell dendrites, where the ganglion cells themselves are neurons that collect all visual information in the retina and send it to the brain. The ganglion cell dendrites then synapse with the bipolar cell axons and form a layer of nerve fibers which will then form the optic nerve axons. With the development of optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) that allows visualization of the fine microvasculature of the retina in layers, several studies have reported retinal microvascular damage in DM patients. Research by Nesper *et al.* found that retinal and choriocapillaris nonperfusion vessels on OCTA correlated significantly with disease severity in eyes with DR (Nesper *et al.*, 2017). More specifically, research by Cao *et al.* found that the density of parafoveal blood vessels in the superficial and deep capillary plexuses was reduced in DM patients (Cao *et al.*, 2018). There is a reciprocal relationship between GC-IPL thinning and

microvascular disorders, where inner retinal thinning can cause microvascular disorders, and retinal perfusion disorders can cause inner retinal atrophy (Lee *et al.*, 2020).

Between treatment doses, it was found that P1 was not significantly different compared to P2 but was significantly different from P3 ($p < 0.05$). The higher the dose of cyclose, the greater the decrease in IPL thickness. The results of this study are consistent with previous results in experimental rats with spontaneous hyperglycemia (Barber *et al.*, 2003), experimental animals of rats and mice with streptozotocin-induced diabetes (Lee *et al.*, 2020 and Barber *et al.*, 2003), and in accordance with DR conditions in the OCTA examination (Nerper *et al.*, 2017 and Cao *et al.*, 2018). This is thought to be due to the influence of increasing blood glucose levels along with increasing doses of sucrose given to each group, resulting in increased ganglion cell apoptosis which causes a decrease in the thickness of the IPL layer of the zebrafish retina (*D. rerio*) (Gleesaon *et al.*, 2007 and Singh *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusions and Suggestions

Induction of 4% sucrose for 28 days was the best dose resulting in increased ganglion cell apoptosis and a decrease in the IPL layer in the zebrafish (*D. rerio*) retina which was in accordance with the picture of diabetic retinopathy in humans.

With the success of this research in producing an experimental animal model of hyperglycemia with retinopathy, future research needs to be continued to test the effectiveness of a drug or natural substance in preventing retinopathy due to increased blood glucose in zebrafish.

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References

- [1] Ranjan, S. and Sharma, P.K., 2018. Development of high sugar induced hyperglycemia or type 2 diabetes in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) model. *Measurement*, 17, p.18.
- [2] Laville, M. and Nazare, J.A., 2009. Diabetes, insulin resistance and sugars. *Obesity reviews*, 10, pp.24-33.
- [3] PERKENI (Perkumpulan Endokrinologi Indonesia). (2021). Pedoman Pengelolaan dan Pencegahan Diabetes Melitus Tipe 2 Dewasa di Indonesia 2021. *In PB PERKENI*. www.ginasthma.org
- [4] Farid, M., Darwin, E., & Sulastri, D. (2014). Pengaruh Hiperglikemia terhadap Gambaran Histopatologis Pulau Langerhans Mencit. *Jurnal Kesehatan Andalas*, 3(3), 420–428. <https://doi.org/10.25077/jka.v3i3.162>
- [5] WHO. (2016) "Global report on adult learning executive summary", *World Organization Health*,3 [Link].
- [6] International Diabetes Federation [IDF]. (2019). "International Diabetes Federation, The Lancet,266(6881),134–137. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(55\)92135-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(55)92135-8)
- [7] Mitchell, P., Suriya F. (2008). Guidelines for the Management of Diabetic Retinopathy. (on line) <http://www.nhmrc.gov.au>. Mitchell, P., Suriya F. (2008). Guidelines for the Management of Diabetic Retinopathy. (on line) <http://www.nhmrc.gov.au>.
- [8] Yang, C., Yu, Y. and An, J., 2024. Effect of High Sucrose Diet on the Occurrence and Progression of Diabetic Retinopathy and Dietary Modification Strategies.
- [9] Ola, M.S., Nawaz, M.I., Khan, H.A. and Alhomida, A.S. (2013). Neurodegeneration and neuroprotection in diabetic retinopathy. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 14(2), pp.2559-2572.
- [10] Gleeson, M., Connaughton, V., & Arneson, L. S. (2007). Induction of hyperglycaemia in zebrafish (*D.rerio*) leads to morphological changes in the retina, *Acta Diabetologica*, 44(3), 157–163. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00592-007-0257-3>
- [11] Septadina, I. S. (2015). Perubahan Anatomi Bola Mata pada Penderita Diabetes Mellitus. *Majalah Kedokteran Sriwijaya*, 47(2), 139-143.Suyono,S. (2009). Diabetes Melitus di Indonesia. Dalam: Sudoyo,Aru W. dkk. (Editor). *Buku Ajar Ilmu Penyakit Dalam* (halaman 1873-1879). Indonesia: Interna Publishing.
- [12] Midena E Angeli CD Blarzino MC. Macular function impairment in eyes with early age-related macular degeneration. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 1997; 38:469±77, 1997
- [13] Shehwana, H., & Konu, O. (2019). Comparative Transcriptomics Between Zebrafish and

- Mammals: A Roadmap for Discovery of Conserved and Unique Signaling Pathways in Physiology and Disease. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 7(2), 1–5. [DOI]
- [14] Jaroszynska, N., Harding, P., & Moosajee, M. (2021). Metabolism in the zebrafish retina. *Journal of Developmental*
- [15] Singh, A., Castillo, H. A., Brown, J., Kaslin, J., Dwyer, K. M., & Gibert, Y. (2019). High glucose levels affect retinal patterning during zebrafish embryogenesis, *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 1–13. [DOI]
- [16] Sharma, P. and Ramachandran, R., 2019. Retina injury and retina tissue preparation to study regeneration in zebrafish. *Bio-protocol*, 9(24), pp.e3466-e34 66.
- [17] Dorsemans, A. C., Lefebvre d'hellencourt, C., Ait-Arsa, I., Jestin, E., Meilhac, O., & Diotel, N. (2017). Acute and chronic models of hyperglycemia in zebrafish: A method to assess the impact of hyperglycemia on neurogenesis and the biodistribution of radiolabeled molecules, *Journal of Visualized Experiments*, 2017(124), 4–11. [DOI]
- [18] Isaac, U. E., Oyo-Ita, E., Igwe, N. P., & Ije, E. L. (2023). Preparation of histology slides and photomicrographs: Indispensable techniques in anatomic education, *Anatomy Journal of Africa*, 12(1), 2252–2262. [DOI]
- [19] Lim, H.B., Shin, Y.I., Lee, M.W., Koo, H., Lee, W.H. and Kim, J.Y., (2020). Ganglion cell–inner plexiform layer damage in diabetic patients: 3-year prospective, longitudinal, observational study. *Scientific reports*, 10(1), p.1470.
- [20] Alfiyah, S. (2024). Hiperglikemi dan Kerusakan Pankreas Yang di Induksi Sukrosa. On going.
- [21] Kowluru RA, Mishra M. (2015). Oxidative stress, mitochondrial damage and diabetic retinopathy. *Biochim Biophys Acta BBA - Mol Basis Dis*, 1;1852(11):2474–83
- [22] Zong H, Ward M, Stitt AW. (2011). AGEs, RAGE, and Diabetic Retinopathy, *Curr Diab Rep*, 1;11(4):244–52.
- [23] Kim, J., Kim, C.S., Lee, Y.M., Sohn, E., Jo, K. and Kim, J.S., (2015). *Litsea japonica* extract inhibits neuronal apoptosis and the accumulation of advanced glycation end products in the diabetic mouse retina. *Molecular Medicine Reports*, 12(1), pp.1075-1081
- [24] Kern, T.S. and Barber, A.J., (2008). Retinal ganglion cells in diabetes. *The Journal of physiology*, 586(18), pp.4401-4408.
- [25] Park, S.H., Park, J.W., Park, S.J., Kim, K.Y., Chung, J.W., Chun, M.H. and Oh, S.J., 2003. Apoptotic death of photoreceptors in the streptozotocin-induced diabetic rat retina. *Diabetologia*, 46, pp.1260-1268.
- [26] Nesper PL, Roberts PK, Onishi AC, et al. (2017). Quantifying microvascular abnormalities with increasing severity of diabetic retinopathy using optical coherence tomography angiography. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*; 58(6): BIO307–BIO315
- [27] Cao D, Yang D, Huang Z, et al. (2018). Optical coherence tomography angiography discerns preclinical diabetic retinopathy in eyes of patients with type 2 diabetes without clinical diabetic retinopathy. *Acta Diabetologica* ; 55(5): 469–477.
- [28] Lee M-W, Lee W-H, Ryu C-K, et al. (2020). Effects of prolonged type 2 diabetes on the inner retinal layer and macular microvasculature: an optical coherence tomography angiography study. *J Clin Med.*; 9(6): 1849.
- [29] Barber AJ, Antonetti DA, Kern TS, Reiter CEN, Soans RS, Krady JK, Levison SW, Gardner TW, Bronson SK (2005) The Ins2Akita mouse as a model of early retinal complications in diabetes. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 46:2210–2218
- [30] Barber A (2003) A new view of diabetic retinopathy: a neurodegenerative disease of the eye. *Prog Neuropsychopharmacol Biol Psychiatry* 27:283–290